

Historical Study of Library Legislation in India

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Abstract:

The study is explored to find out historical information and importance of Indian public library legislations. Because legislation provides financial support and controls all the activities of public libraries. And in the world, public libraries are known as a people university and it provides the service on the basis of equality.

Keywords: Library legislation, Public Library legislation, Indian library legislation.

1. Introduction

The library development in any country is mostly related with cultural, social, political development of that country. By the great efforts of Maharaja Sayajirao Gaikwad III, The Baroda was the first state in India that focused on for origination public library system in modern sense and The Baroda has developed a library network in the state. Maharaja Sayaji Rao Gaikwad III had travelled all over the world and he impressed by role of public libraries in promotion of education in United States in 1910. Then he thought to invite an American expert, William Allon Borden for organizing the public library system in Baroda. The developed system by him is consists of central library at the apex, many branch libraries and travelling libraries with special provision for women and children and also audio-visual section.^[1]

The Legislation is a meaning of Law or Act. In the library context, the library legislation or act is the meaning of giving legal provision for establishing a library system, library maintenance, services, functions and management under any state or a central government. Library legislation has capability of regulating various parts of public library services. It is an important instrument for developing the public libraries in a planned manner to ensure that to establish, develop and maintain of libraries in a uniform pattern. Legislation can help to promote for creating self-consciousness among the people those who feel it difficulty on their part to use services offered by the library. In the world, the Great Britain passed the first library act in the year of 1850. Till the present all the countries are specifying free use of public library services.^[2]

Firstly, the Baroda state had established public library system prior to 1945. Then first act was passed as the name of Kolhapur public act. There was the first initiative followed in 1948 by Madras Public Library Act passed in newly independent republic of India.^[6]

2. Objectives of the study:

Followings are the objectives of research article:

- i. To study the historical background of library legislation in India
- ii. To understand the need of library legislation
- iii. To review the existing library legislations in India

3. Methodology of Study:

This study is brought out on the base of primary and secondary literature, it consists books, theses chapters, journal article etc. The Internet was used to collect relevant literature.

4. Need of the Library Legislation:

Public library service gives a natural corollary to the democratic way of life. There is necessary of free communication for the preservation of a free society and creative culture. Expectation of public library is that users should only spend their time and not spend money for the using services. In this kind of situation, the question arises, from where will the finance come for public library? This is the answer that the legislation is effectively provides the finance for library. The need of Library Legislation is following:

- To helps in creating necessary conditions under which public libraries can be established nationwide.
- To provide enough and sure financial support public library by way of levy of library tax.
- To make independence to the public library from subscription, donation or private gift and to save the library from political influence.
- To setup administration with permanent, uniform, efficient, balanced and coordinated library service and also for proper line of growth.

- To solve the issue of land, building, legacies, etc.
- For centralized services like acquisition, processing, etc.

The provision of financial support to the public libraries is contained in library legislation, but it is depend upon the social, political and economic environment. Followings are two ways for making provision of finance to public libraries through library legislation:

- Allocation of annual budget by the state out of its total funds with capital grants from central government.
- Match the grant from state government and Levy of library cess.^{[1][2][3][5]}

5. Characteristics of Library Legislation

Characteristics of library legislation are following-

- i) The constitution of library legislation must be simple and general.
- ii) It should be independent from political influence or political pressure.
- iii) Defining of clear responsibility must be as per local, state and national government.
- iv) It must mention the library service are compulsory and free to one and all.
- v) It should make environment for libraries to flourish.
- vi) Legislation must Coordinate and control activities of library in full recognition of the people to have free access to the information and knowledge.
- vii) It must catch each reader interest.
- viii) Different types of tasks should be assigned for each kind of library based on specialization to ensure a better service to the community with the least cost.^{[1][3]}

6. Existing Library Legislation in India

6.1 Madras Public Library Act

Madras Public Libraries Act is also known as Tamilnadu Public Libraries Act. It was enacted in 1948 in India. This was first legislation in India after independent. Connemara Public Library is the library come first under the purview of this act as a State Central Library. Then during 1951 five year plan, nine district libraries were added. The act was based on research and activity of Dr. S. R. Ranganatahn and the Madras Library Association. Then other states also constituted library legislation on the base of Madras Public Library Act.^{[7][8]}

6.2 Andhra Pradesh Public Library Act

State of Andhra Pradesh was formed in 1956 by eleven districts in Andra region and nine districts from Telangana region were merged in the State. Andhra Pradesh was a second state to enact library legislation in 1960. The legislation was passed by the inspiration of Madras Public library Act 1948. There was faced some administrative difficulties in operation together of Madras public library act 1948 in Andhra area and Hyderabad Public Library Act 1955 in Telangana area. So the 1960s, Andhra Pradesh act was brought out by integrating both acts. Later the act was amended in 1964, 1969, 1987 and 1989.^{[9][2]}

6.3 Karnataka Public Library Act

Karnataka was enacted Public library act in 1965. It is third state in India that enacted Public Library legislation. The Public library act preamble states that 'An Act to provide for the establishment and maintenance of public libraries and the organization of a comprehensive rural and urban library service in the State of Mysore'. Education department guides and controls to activities of public libraries. Head of the Department of Public Libraries is the state librarian. Director of public libraries is heading the department at the present situation.^[9]

6.4 Maharashtra Public Library Act

The state of Maharashtra was struggled hard for enacting Public Library Act. The all movement started in the year 1936 when the Bombay Presidency Public Library Bill was introduced in the legislature in 1936, but the act was not considered. The Congress Ministry of Bombay appointed a Library Development Committee in 1939. As a chairmanship of A.A.Pyzee, the proposal was made for the promotion of public library service in the state. At the time Committee had prepared Report, unfortunately, the Ministry of Congress had resigned. The Report was stayed pending in cold storage all through the period of World War II. The recommendations of the Pyzee Committee relating to the development of urban public libraries, the action began to be taken when the second popular ministry assumed office.

Another effort in 1944, the state of Kolhapur (now forming part of the present Maharashtra state) passed the Kolhapur Public Libraries Act. The act was given provision to appointment of Curator under the Director of Education.

By the R. S. Parkhi in 1944, the third attempt was made. At his request the bill was drafted for the composite state of Bombay. In 1947, it was published by the Junior Raja of Aundh under the title "Library

Development plan with a draft library Bill and a thirty year programme." Then the Bill copy was submitted to the then Chief Minister, B. G.Kher. Latter hewas convinced about its utility, but due to bureaucratic inertia, nothing came out of it.

In 1959, The Maharashtra GranthalayaSangh had taken initiative and again in 1965 for the enactment of library legislation. However, their efforts were not got success. In 1967, the State Government drafted a Library Bill and this was passed in July 1967.^[10]

6.5 West Bengal Public Libraries Act

West Bengal is a third state to pass library legislation in India. West Bengal was played pioneer role in the field of library movement in India. The legislative council of public library bill was first introduced on the basis of Model bill by Dr. S. R. Ranganathan and Munindra Deb Roy of Calcutta, who was president of Bengal library association to suit the continuation of Bengal, but the Governor-General not permitted its introduction into Bengal Legislative Council because of the compulsory clauses of the Bill.⁴⁴ After that the Government constituted an expert committee to draft a Public Library act for enactment. This Committee members were connected since many years to library movement. The committee prepared draft bill and after some modification it was enacted in 1979. Then also amended in 1982 and 1985.

6.6 Manipur Public Libraries Act

Manipur is small state, located in eastern part of India. The state got opportunity to constitute library legislation and passed the act as Manipur Library Legislation in 1988.^[11]

6.7 Kerala Public Libraries Act

Kerala state had passed the Act of public library legislation in 1989. The Kerala Library legislation is quite different one than other states acts. But the act is unique because of its democratic and more decentralized pattern.

6.8 Haryana Public Libraries Act

Haryana state also passed the act of Public library in 1989 for providing for the establishment, maintenance and development of Public Libraries in the State of Haryana.

6.9 Mizoram Public Libraries Act

Mizoram state became a full-fledged in 1987. Within five years, in 1993 it enacted the library Act as Mizoram Public Library Act.

6.10 Goa Public Libraries Act

Goa is the tenth State to enact public library legislation in India. The Act was passed in the year of 1993.

6.11 Gujarat Public Libraries Act

Public Library act was passed by Gujarat State in 2001. Following salient features of the act:

- 1) Constitution of the State Library Development Council, with Minister in Charge of Library as its Ex-officio, President.
- 2) Constitution of Directorate of Public Libraries for monitoring the system.
- 3) Establishment of District and Taluka Libraries and association.^[12]

6.12 Orissa Public Libraries Act

Orissa state enacted the act in 2001 as an Orissa public library act in India. The act was constituted for establishment network the public libraries situated in Orissa state. It also maintains, regulate, guide, control, supervise, integrate and consolidate the libraries in Orissa state.

6.13 Uttarakhand (Uttaranchal) Public Libraries Act

After separating the state from Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand was enacted library legislation in 2005 on the demand of Uttarakhand people.^{[12][15]}

6.14 Uttar Pradesh Public Libraries Act

The state Uttar Pradesh was passed the bill of Public library legislation in 2006 to establish, maintain, regulate and control the public libraries in Uttar Pradesh.^{[14][15]}

6.15 Rajasthan Public Libraries Act

The Rajyasthan Librarian Association was submitted library bill to Government in 1965. After serious efforts of Rajyasthan library association, the public library act was passed in 2006 as the name of Rajyasthan public library act.^[15]

6.16 Bihar Public Libraries Act

Bihar Library Association was established in 1936. This Association drafted bill of public library act and submitted to Government. Then the library legislation was enacted in 2008 in Bihar.^[12]

6.17 Chattisgarh Public Libraries Act

Chattisgarh is a state separated from Madhya Pradesh. Most of the part of state is backward so the people was demanded to have public library at every district. In 2008, Chattisgarh Public Library Act was passed.^[15]

6.18 Pondicherry Public Libraries Act, 2007^[13]

6.19 Arunachal Pradesh Public Libraries Act, 2009^[13]

7. Findings and Conclusion:

From the present study, it is found that...

- ✓ Library has great history of establishment of library.
- ✓ By comparing to the Western countries library legislation act, India enacted library act too late.
- ✓ All states are not formed public library Act/ legislation in India.

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